
MEASURES TO ENSURE ENERGY SECURITY IN THE REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7830793>

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Abstract.

In this article, based on the analysis of energy security measures and weak points in the Republic of Uzbekistan, by showing what types of energy sources have a priority in economic and social development, forming a modern vision of nuclear energy sources with a high level of security in students. methods are shown.

Key words.

Energy, security, modern, resources, hydropower, identified deficiencies, elimination.

Introduction.

It is known that at the current stage of development of the world community, the demand for energy consumption is growing much faster than the rate of its production. Taking into account industry, economic growth, and population growth in the 21st century, it is estimated that the energy consumed by mankind in the next fifty years will be more than the energy used in its entire history. That is why the issue of energy supply is becoming increasingly acute, and the desire to increase the efficiency of the use of various energy sources is becoming a competitive struggle all over the world. Indeed, as V. I. Fistul, a professor of Moscow State University, noted, the most accurate measure of the state's development level in the future will be the amount of energy per person per unit of time. Taking into account all the requirements of the modern development of the society, the question of how to increase the role of the obtained electric energy has not yet been answered, and different countries, based on their internal conditions, evaluate one or another source as a priority. In this regard, taking into account all the beneficial and harmful aspects of energy production, it is one of the most important issues for all countries to develop their economy by determining the type of energy sources that are convenient and more likely to be chosen for them.

Main part

The increasing problem of non-renewable fuel power stations, such as fossil oil, gas, coal, which are traditionally used as energy sources, is their limitation, cost of use, and huge damage to the environment. Therefore, in order to get out of this situation, efforts to switch to an alternative type of blue (green) energy are gaining momentum.

Rust energy is also known as renewable energy. According to the information of the international agency, the share of blue energy in the total energy is observed to increase. Alternative types of sources include solar, wind, geothermal power plants, small hydroelectric power plants, bioenergy facilities, waste treatment facilities, and tidal and tidal energy from the sea and oceans.

In this, three-quarters of the renewable energies correspond to solar and wind energy. It can be seen from these that all energy sources have their own characteristics, and the most optimal options should be selected only after a comprehensive assessment of all causes and consequences of their use. Energy is a national economy that includes the creation of various types of energy, their transformation from one type to another, their transmission and delivery over a certain distance, their use in all areas, and the solution of theoretical and practical problems related to them. , is the field of science and technology. Coal, oil, natural gas, peat, wood, shale, water, electric and nuclear energy, wind and solar energy are energy resources.

The future development of the country's hydropower is mainly related to the use of hydro resources of small water bodies.

The concepts of "energy security" and "energy sustainability" are very important for every country and have a great impact on the way of life of its inhabitants. Therefore, it is natural that some questions arise: what is the primary energy source reserves of the modern world and each country, how long will these reserves last, their rational use, the impact of energy on the environment, etc.

The essence of energy security and the importance of ensuring it. Energy security is one of the important components of national, including economic, security. Energy security is a state of protection of the entire world, society, country and citizens, as well as their economy, from the scarcity and shortage of fuel and energy resources of a certain quality level that can be economically obtained under the influence of internal and external threat factors.

The essence of the concept of "energy security". The amount that the whole world, society, country, citizens and their economy can economically receive under the

influence of internal and external threat factors is the state of being protected from shortage of fuel and energy resources of a certain quality level.

Energy security also represents the sustainable development of energy resources and energy production, the country's self-sufficiency with them, and the efficiency of energy production and consumption.

There are threats to energy security in Uzbekistan and the Central Asian region, which include:

- high level of wear and tear of the main equipment in the branches of the fuel energy complex;
- weak interaction between centers of development (extraction) of energy resources and their consumers in the fuel and energy sector in the countries of the region;
- that the economy has not been transferred to the path of energy saving development;
- lack of investment in energy sectors and low efficiency of their use;
- low purchasing power of domestic energy consumers and importers of energy carriers;
- the fact that cases of failure to pay for the consumption of energy and energy resources are widespread;

The absence of a mutually beneficial agreement between the countries of Central Asia between the owners of energy-carrying resources and the countries that produce and consume energy from them.

In order to ensure energy security in Uzbekistan, it will be necessary to use internal capabilities and implement the following:

- further development of lignite open pit mining;
- increasing and stabilizing natural gas production to a certain extent;
- maintaining the achieved level of production of liquid carbohydrates;
- development of underground gasification of coal;
- expansion of processes of deep processing of carbohydrate raw materials;
- raising the quality of energy products to world standards;
- maintaining the achieved balance in terms of electricity;
- achieving energy resource savings;
- achieving mutually beneficial and reliable cooperation in the field of energy.

Conclusion

To sum up, by the decision of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. 638 of October 9, 2020, the control inspection in the field of electric power under the Ministry of Energy of the Republic of Uzbekistan has been assigned constant control over compliance with the rules of safety equipment in the operation of electrical equipment in power plants. installation is loaded. Accordingly, detailed explanations of organizational and technical measures for the safe execution of work were given to the employees of the division, and discussions were held to prevent accidents that occurred in the field in the future.

Development of a plan of actions to eliminate identified shortcomings, instructions for quick elimination, prevention of emergency shutdowns of electrical equipment and injuries to employees, and ensuring the continuity of electricity supply to economic sectors, social sector objects, and residents' homes. was given and the execution of the instructions was controlled.

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